

THE ROLE OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL AND NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS IN PROTECTING WOMEN IN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a scientific-theoretical analysis of innovative processes occurring in the social, cultural, and spiritual spheres of women's lives in Uzbekistan. It discusses the legal foundations for ensuring equal rights and opportunities between men and women, as well as the content and essence of national and international legal documents regarding gender equality. Furthermore, the article highlights the importance of cooperation between state policy, non-governmental organizations, and international institutions in improving the system of social protection for women. Based on innovative approaches, the study examines ways to enhance women's socio-political activity, strengthen their position in society, and develop human capital. The results of the research have practical and scientific significance in further improving social policies aimed at supporting women

Introduction

Full and genuine equality between men and women is a crucial element of a just and democratic society based on the rule of law. The holistic development of society and the well-being of all its members necessitate equal opportunities for men and women to participate fully. The full and equal enjoyment of human rights by women is of paramount importance for strengthening peace and democracy in the country. In Uzbekistan, women constitute more than 50% of the population; therefore, their intellectual and spiritual development, as well as social, economic, and political-legal activity, is not only vital for national development but also essential for the stability of families.

Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrines the principle of equal rights for men and women. On May 6, 1995, Uzbekistan acceded to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (adopted in New York on December 18, 1979) [1], the Convention on the Political Rights of Women (August 30, 1997) [2], and the convention on equal remuneration for men and women for work of equal value. These steps, based on internationally recognized legal norms while taking into account the national mentality, laid the foundation for ensuring equal rights and opportunities for men and women in Uzbekistan.

Literature Review and Methodology

The social-philosophical and sociological aspects of preventing domestic violence in Uzbekistan have been studied in the works of scholars such as N.M. Latipova, O. Musurmonova, N.R. Nishonova, M.X. Xolmatova, G. M. Matkarimova, X. Nasrullayeva, N. Jo'rayeva, M. Nurmatova, E. Sultonova, S.X. Safayeva, Sh. Sodiqova, G.J. G'aniyeva, and M.Q. G'afforova.

Among the scholars from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), L.I. Amanbayeva, A.V. Belyayev, M.V. Bogomaz, L.S. Vygotsky, Dj. Karpara, V.A. Sitarov, and G.K. Selevkolar conducted research on the socio-psychological aspects of preventing domestic violence, while G.M. Andreyeva, V.V. Antipov, L.P. Bogdanova, A. Varga, I.F. Dementyeva, T.R. Kirimov, P.R. Novikov, YE.G. Silyayeva, and L.B. Shneyder examined interpersonal relationships within families and highlighted the necessity of psychological services and counseling in preventing family conflicts.

The role of a gender-based approach and gender identity issues in combating domestic violence has also been extensively studied in international research. Scholars investigating these issues from a constructive paradigm perspective include R. Connell, P. Bourdieu, Dj. Scott, V. Spike Peterson, and O.A. Voronin. Additionally, prominent international researchers such as N. Najib, E. Helen, A. Kitchen, M. Kovalskiy, D. Ruts, and L. Husniyk have conducted studies on women's social protection, providing recommendations on legal solutions for domestic violence cases and on assisting women in overcoming psychological distress.

Results and Discussion

Documents concerning gender equality between men and women were adopted in Madrid (1983), Vienna (1989), Moscow (1991), Istanbul (1999), Maastricht (2003), Sofia (2004), Ljubljana (2005), and Athens (2009). These normative legal documents contributed to improving the global effectiveness of social protection systems for women.

In Uzbekistan, the Laws No. 561 "On the Protection of Women from Pressure and Violence" and No. 562 "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" were adopted on September 2, 2019. In addition, more than 15 regulatory legal acts were adopted to fundamentally improve the system of social protection for women, indicating that this issue in the country has reached international standards.

The Decree No. 5325 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated February 2, 2018, "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve Activities in Supporting Women and Strengthening the Institution of the Family," as well as Decree PQ-3827 of July 2, 2018, "On Measures to Improve the System of Social Rehabilitation and Adaptation, as well as the Prevention of Domestic Violence," and Decree PQ-4235 of March 7, 2019, "On Measures to Further Strengthen Guarantees of Women's Labor Rights and Support Entrepreneurial Activities," were adopted to strengthen legal and institutional mechanisms.

According to the fifth periodic report submitted by Uzbekistan in 2019 on the full implementation of the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, one of the recommendations of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women was the adoption of a law guaranteeing the practical implementation of gender equality between men and women.

According to the Convention, participating states, in the context of efforts to eliminate discrimination against women, are obliged to:

- Incorporate the principle of equality between men and women into the national legal system, repeal all laws that create grounds for discrimination against women, and adopt appropriate laws prohibiting any form of discrimination against women;
- Take all necessary measures, including legislative improvements, to ensure women's full participation in all spheres, including political, social, economic, and cultural, and to enable them to realize their potential;
- Implement temporary special measures to accelerate the achievement of practical equality for women;
- Undertake obligations to eliminate social norms and views that give preference to one gender over another.

Based on these international principles and requirements, unprecedented reforms have been carried out in Uzbekistan to establish the legal and social foundations for enhancing the status and influence of women. The Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" has established legal equality for women with men in all spheres throughout the country.

Specifically, in the nationwide elections for the heads of citizens' assemblies held in May 2019, 1,025 women were elected to leadership positions in local self-governing bodies. The responsibility for decision-making is increasingly entrusted to women, and the proportion of female managers in various enterprises rose from 27.2% in 2016 to 45.3% in 2019.

Currently, nearly all political parties have at least one female deputy leader, with dedicated women's wings. Approximately 700 non-governmental organizations (NGOs) work on women's issues. To coordinate the activities of NGOs, share experiences, and improve the social service infrastructure, a national forum on "The Experience of NGOs in Increasing the Socio-Political Activity of Women" was held in February 2019. As a result of the forum, the "NGO Club" focusing on women's issues was established.

At present, the Club has 58 members. Within the framework of this Club, a social services cluster has been developed. Legal clinics for women were established in cooperation with NGOs in the Qashqadaryo, Khorezm, Fergana, and Karakalpakstan regions.

To strengthen the activities and material-technical base of NGOs and shelters, UNICEF provided financial assistance amounting to USD 56,000. International organizations contributed USD 20,000 to support the activities of the NGOs "Aydin Nur," "Rahmdillik," "Mehr Kuzda," and "Nihol."

During field receptions, the problems of 63 women were studied on-site and practical assistance was provided. The objective was to save women the expenses of traveling to Tashkent and to address their urgent issues locally.

The NGO "Istiqbolli Avlod" provided practical assistance to 12 women who were victims of human trafficking and facilitated their return to their families. In cooperation with the "Sabr" Social Development NGO, 340 women received psychological, legal, social, and medical support, and 17 mobile reception events were organized.

The "Sharq Ayoli" Foundation has organized activities aimed at enhancing the role and status of women, including the traditional annual "Woman of the Year" competition.

With the support of the Center for Civil Initiatives, local authorities, ministries, and agencies have conducted outreach activities to explain the provisions of the CEDAW Convention

and raise awareness among the population. To date, more than 40 roundtable discussions have been held across eight regions on this topic.

In cooperation with the NGO “Nixol,” programs have been adopted to support young girls, develop their abilities comprehensively, and prepare them for independent life.

To strengthen cooperation with international organizations, annual joint plans have been developed and approved in collaboration with UNICEF, UNFPA, UNODC, UNDP, and the OSCE based on bilateral proposals. A “Roadmap” was developed for cooperation with the International Organization for Migration.

Monitoring the Implementation of the CEDAW Convention in the Regions

Sociological research was conducted using observation methods by monitoring group members in Bukhara, Jizzakh, and Andijan regions regarding the implementation of the CEDAW Convention. Based on the results, roundtable discussions were held with expert specialists and experienced practitioners.

According to the conducted work and research results, certain shortcomings were identified in coordinating the activities of NGOs addressing women’s issues within the system of the Committee on Women. In particular:

- Cooperation with NGOs working on women’s issues is not at the required level, not only with large and resourceful NGOs but also with small initiative-driven organizations;
- No monitoring system has been established for projects implemented by NGOs targeting women;
- The potential of trained NGO representatives within project frameworks is not being fully utilized;
- Reports and information on activities conducted in collaboration with NGOs do not meet established standards.

To address these shortcomings, the following measures are recommended:

- Develop and implement a Concept aimed at improving NGO partnership activities, coordinating cooperation to enhance women’s status in society and within families in Uzbekistan, and strengthening social partnerships;
- The Senate Committee on Women and Gender Issues of the Oliy Majlis and the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support should collaborate with NGOs addressing women’s and family issues to jointly implement tasks set in annually adopted State Programs, thereby strengthening the role of NGOs in solving women’s and family problems and attracting international organizations and grants to improve their material and technical base;
- The Senate Committee on Women and Gender Issues, the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support, and its regional departments should, in cooperation with local NGOs, organize events aimed at: improving the moral environment in families, enhancing women’s and children’s health, supporting entrepreneurship for women and girls, preventing various negative indicators, and fostering civil society. These activities may include meetings, roundtable discussions, video conferences, competitions, review contests, training programs, and other initiatives, based on national and international legal frameworks, social partnerships, and public oversight;

• The Senate Committee on Women and Gender Issues, the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support, the Ministry of Justice, the Independent Institute for Civil Society Formation and Monitoring and its regional branches, the National Association of NGOs of Uzbekistan, the regional branches of the Republican Council for Spirituality and Enlightenment, regional hokimiyats, and other relevant institutions should organize events on topics such as “The Role and Importance of Social Partnership in Forming Civil Society,” “Social Partnership,” and “The Role of Women’s Committees in Implementing the Law and Prospective Cooperation.”

Conclusion

Based on the results of public opinion research, respondents involved in the observation process believe that NGOs and other civil society institutions in Uzbekistan have been provided with sufficient opportunities to participate in elections.

Awareness of these opportunities and their effective use has contributed not only to conducting elections in a democratic spirit but also to the development of civil society in Uzbekistan. Such cooperation enhances the potential of women, strengthens their leadership abilities, allows them to manifest themselves as politicians, managers, and public figures, and ensures their broader participation in the ongoing social, political, economic, informational, and ideological reforms in the country.

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